

Thermodynamic and Structural Studies of Chelates of 2-Hydroxyphenyl-4-benzamidothiosemicarbazide with Cerium(IV) and Uranium(VI)

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Manuscript received 10 January 1985, revised 19 August 1985, accepted 15 November 1985

Interaction between Ce^{IV} and U^{VI} with 2-hydroxyphenyl-4-benzamidothiosemicarbazide has been studied. Spectrophotometric, electrometric and chemical analysis give 1 : 2 metal-ligand ratio. Stepwise stability constants have been calculated pH-metrically at different ionic strengths and at different temperatures. Thermodynamic parameters have been calculated which reveal exothermic interaction between metal and ligand and support the formation of stable complexes. The complexes have been characterised by IR studies.

EXTENSIVE stoichiometric and structural studies of Cr^{III} , Mn^{II} , Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} and Ag^{I} complexes of 2-hydroxyphenyl-4-benzamidothiosemicarbazide have been reported earlier^{1,2}. In this communication, characterisation and thermodynamic parameters of Ce^{IV} and U^{VI} complexes of this ligand have been reported.

Experimental

Fresh solution of 2-hydroxyphenyl-4-benzamidothiosemicarbazide (OH-BTSC) was used. Stock solutions of ceric ammonium nitrate and uranyl acetate were prepared in CO_2 -free double-distilled water and their strengths were calculated by the usual methods. All the chemicals were of AnalaR and B.P. grade. Optical measurements were made on a Bausch and Lomb Spectronic-20 spectrophotometer. The pH titrations at different temperatures and amperometric titrations at -0.4 V (selected from the plateaux of OH-BTSC) vs SCE were carried out as reported earlier^{1,3}. The pH-values were corrected⁴ for mixed solvents.

Equimolar solutions of ceric ammonium nitrate and OH-BTSC were mixed with stirring in a 1 : 2 stoichiometric ratio. pH of the solution was raised to about 9.0 for separation of the complex. The cerium(IV) complex was centrifuged, washed with water and finally recrystallised from acetone and dried in vacuum desiccator. Uranium(VI) complex, being highly soluble in water, was isolated by mixing equimolar solutions of metal ions and ligand in acetone-ethanol mixture (90 : 10, v/v) at $pH \approx 9.5$. The complex was recrystallised from acetone.

The solid complexes were analysed for elements to ascertain their composition. Uranium was estimated gravimetrically as U_3O_8 and cerium(IV) was estimated volumetrically by titration with standard iron(II) solution. Nitrogen was estimated microanalytically by Dumas method and sulphur as $BaSO_4$. The results of chemical analysis are given in Table 1. IR spectra of ligand and metal complexes were recorded in KBr medium on a Beckman-20 spectrophotometer. Magnetic measurements of the complexes were made on the Gouy's magnetic balance at 30° .

TABLE 1 ANALYTICAL DATA

Compd.	Analysis % Found/(Calcd.)		
	Metal	N	S
$(C_{16}H_{12}N_4O_8S_2)U$	31.35 (31.47)	14.75 (14.81)	8.55 (8.48)
$(C_{16}H_{12}N_4O_7S_2)Ce$	21.78 (21.81)	17.65 (17.43)	10.56 (9.98)

Results and Discussion

Preliminary studies reveal that metal salt solutions when mixed with OH-BTSC gave dark brownish orange and orange coloured solutions with Ce^{IV} and U^{VI} , respectively. Conductivity measurements for the uranium complex in non-polar solvents show its ionic nature while Ce^{IV} complex is non-ionic.

Vosburgh-Cooper's curves⁵ indicated complexation as the λ_{max} values 385 nm and 445 nm, occurring in the absorption spectra of Ce^{IV} and U^{VI} metal ions were shifted to 370 nm and uv region, respectively in the presence of ligand. Wavelength

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region 480-520 nm was chosen for absorption measurements since in this region, the complexes absorb appreciably high as compared to the reactants. Normal Job's⁶ and slope-ratio⁷ curves were obtained. Job's curves peaked at 0.33 mole fraction corresponding to 1 : 2 M-L ratio and the slope of curves 1, 2 and 3, 4 for Ce^{IV} and U^{VI}, respectively (Fig. 1) further showed 1 : 2 M-L ratio for both the complexes. Amperometric studies also confirmed 1 : 2 stoichiometry for these complexes.

Fig. 1

The *pK* values of OH-BTSC were determined *pH*-metrically at 26 and 32° at different ionic strengths. These values did not differ appreciably and were found to be almost the same, 8.5 and 10.2. Maximum lowering in case of 1 : 2 metal-OH-BTSC mixture and inflection corresponding to 4 moles of KOH : 1 mole of metal indicated 1 : 2 metal-ligand ratio in the complexes.

At 26 and 32°, *pH*-titrations of OH-BTSC alone and in presence of different concentrations of metal ions, at different ionic strengths (only in the case of uranium, constant ionic strength could be maintained), were performed according to Calvin and Melchior⁸, gave normal titration curves when titrated against 0.1 *M* KOH; and from these the formation curves were constructed. The *pL* values at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and 1.5 gave the values of stepwise stability constants, $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$, and of overall stability constant, $\log K$ (Table 2). In the case of uranium complex, overall stability constants were calculated graphically at zero ionic strength (Fig. 2, curves 1, 2; Table 2). For cerium complex, the apparent average values of $\log K$ are 29.46 and 29.02 at 26 and 32°, respectively.

TABLE 2

Temp °C	Values of $\log K$ at different ionic strengths for U ^{VI} complex			
	0.067 <i>M</i>	0.133 <i>M</i>	0.200 <i>M</i>	0.00 <i>M</i>
26	18.94	19.20	19.39	18.77
32	18.78	18.97	19.23	18.50

Fig. 2

From the knowledge of overall stability constants, thermodynamic parameters, *viz.* ΔH° , ΔG° , ΔS° were calculated at 26° (Table 3). It is clear from the *pH* data that $\bar{n}$ increases with the increase in *pH* values upto $\bar{n}=2$, showing thereby that the ionic form of the ligand takes part in the reaction and further proves 1 : 2 metal-ligand ratio in the complexes. Furthermore, the reaction between metal ion and OH-BTSC is exothermic and proceeds spontaneously as indicated by the respective negative values of ΔH° and ΔG° . Positive values of ΔS° confirm the formation of stable complexes.

TABLE 3—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS AT 26°

Compd.	G° kJ mol ⁻¹	H° kJ mol ⁻¹	S° JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
(C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂)U	-107.458	-78.575	+96.60
(C ₁₂ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₃ S ₂)Ce	-168.658	-125.139	+145.50

A sharp band at 3 555 cm⁻¹ in the ir spectrum of OH-BTSC has been assigned to the phenolic group, which disappeared in the spectra of the metal chelates, suggesting the loss of phenolic hydrogen on complexation, establishing a bond between metal and phenolic oxygen in these complexes. The sharp band at 1 610 cm⁻¹ observed in OH-BTSC spectrum is due to the bending vibrations of amino and amide groups. This band is shifted to 1 620 cm⁻¹ in both the complexes, suggesting the non-involvement of amido nitrogen in complex formation. However, the decrease in the intensity and lowering of absorption band from 1 200 to 1 160 cm⁻¹ due to N—C—S bending plus NH₂ rocking and NH₂ deformation in these complexes, support the metal-nitrogen (attached to imido nitrogen atom) bonding. The sharp absorption bands in OH-BTSC occurring at 3 300, 3 285 and 3 200 cm⁻¹ are due to the NH and NH₂ stretching frequencies. These vibrations in the Ce^{IV} complex have been broadened in the region 3 200-3 480 cm⁻¹, and two broad bands in the region 3 400-3 520 and 3 200-3 320 cm⁻¹ for U^{VI} complex are observed. The shifting of the NH—NH₂ vibrations to the higher wavelengths suggests the non-

